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On the contribution of intermediary organizations to knowledge sharing¹

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Introduction

For many years, research on innovation systems, triple helix models of innovation, innovation ecosystems, or Open Innovation has focused on the contributions of actors outside of companies to their innovation success. An important player in this context are the universities and research institutions, which produce new knowledge through research and share it with companies through many different mechanisms, such as publications, qualified graduates, research partnerships, or knowledge and technology transfer (KTT) by means of patents, licenses, and academic spin-offs.

In order to support their outreach to business and society, universities and research institutions have established (mostly internal) knowledge transfer offices (KTOs), and a broad set of further intermediary organizations (IOs) has emerged. The impact of IOs has been investigated before, however, usually one or few IOs and the impact on corporate beneficiaries have been put in the centre of attention. Less frequently, analyses have included a wider set of IOs. Moreover, the relationship between IOs and academic researchers, respectively the impact on academic KTT activities, has been somewhat neglected (with the exceptions of Minguillo & Thelwall, 2015; Clayton, Feldman, & Lowe, 2018). This is not satisfying, as IOs are often a key element of transfer policy initiatives (Fini, Rasmussen, Siegel, & Wiklund, 2018). Our work intends therefore to contribute to closing this research gap.

The present paper focuses on three questions:

1. Which IOs are important for supporting KTT activities from the perspective of academic institutions?
2. Which characteristics and activities of IOs contribute to raising their importance?
3. Which mechanisms or channels of KTT are affected most by IOs?

Current understanding

Knowledge transfer intermediation has been described as a process of managed and targeted facilitation between universities and industrial partners (Albats, Alexander, & Cunningham,

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2022). Howells (2006, p. 720) has defined an intermediary organization as an organization “that acts an agent or broker in any aspect of the innovation process between two or more parties”. Related constructs are boundary organizations (Guston, 2001) and knowledge brokers (Meyer, 2010). We combine these under the headline of intermediary organizations (IOs) and include different types of organizations which work with scientists to help them sharing their knowledge and technologies with their audiences outside science; sharing includes activities like transferring, co-creating, or commercializing.

Albats, Alexander and Cunningham (2022) suggest describing and analyzing knowledge transfer intermediaries along two dimensions: a) a structural dimension that focuses on their structural characteristics, knowledge ownership and governance, and b) an agency dimension relating to their functions or activities and how these are regulated. They identify 14 structural variables such as location, disciplinary scope, ownership, or resources, and 12 activities, including gatekeeping and brokering, IP management, commercialization etc.; in their qualitative study of 20 intermediaries they distinguish three clusters:

- 1) Traditional intermediaries in the sense of knowledge and technology transfer offices established by a higher education institution that owns the IP, commercializes it and engages in a broad range of activities;
- 2) Regional-cluster intermediaries established at regional level and serving the institutions of the region mainly with knowledge (re-)combination (in the sense of Howells, 2006), diffusion, gatekeeping/brokering, and testing/validation;
- 3) Digital intermediaries which are private or at least independent of a particular institution and provide information scanning and processing, matchmaking, knowledge combination often on a fee basis.

As this work has shown, the tasks and approaches of the different types of IOs are similar but not identical and even though they mostly focus on reducing the distance between the academic and the business world, they may cover different dimensions of this distance, e.g., its cognitive, geographical, organizational, or social dimension (Villani, Rasmussen, & Grimaldi, 2017). The existence of a KTO is positively correlated with the amount of KTT of universities and research institutions (Ambos, Makela, Birkinshaw, & D’Este, 2008) and their patenting performance (Temel et al., 2021). They create cognitive proximity between science and industry by reducing bureaucratic entry and cooperation barriers, hiring “hybrid” personnel who are at home in both cultures, and technology scouting (internal) or partner scouting (external) (Villani et al., 2017). The results on the relationship between incubators and knowledge sharing are mixed. In a study on British incubators and innovation parks, Minguillo and Thelwall (2015) come to the conclusion that neither patents nor research or consultancy contracts are higher in universities linked to incubators. There is, however, a significant correlation with the number of spin-offs and, consequently, with the utilisation of the facilities and laboratories available at the university. The results for Spain are very similar (Caldera & Debande, 2010). Work on proof-of-concept centres at US universities has found positive effects on academic entrepreneurship (Hayter & Link, 2015), and cooperative research centres have been found to raise research collaborations with the industry at US research universities (Boardman & Corley, 2008).

Research design

Dataset

The empirical basis of this analysis is a cross-sectional dataset resulting from an online survey of the heads of research institutes. Institutes were understood to be scientific organizational units that carry out R&D projects and whose heads have project and personnel responsibility

for 10 to 50 persons. In 39 universities and research organizations in Switzerland, we identified 2'032 such institutes in 28 fields of science, which were then invited to participate in the online survey. 49 institutes were subsequently excluded for different reasons, e.g., they no longer existed or were just recently founded and unable to report on the period of observation 2015-17. Of the remaining 1'983 institutes, 943 (47.6%) answered the questions; however, due to item missing values 477-564 could be included in the data analyses for this paper.

Constructs

We measured the performance of an institute for three mechanisms or channels of knowledge sharing: 1) knowledge commercialization in the form of self-reported patent applications, license contracts and spin-offs; 2) teaching-based knowledge sharing through measures for the number of Bachelor and Master theses written in cooperation with firms, and the number of theses supervised in further education programs; 3) research-based knowledge sharing, which was assessed through an index for the importance of joint project work with companies, another index for the importance of informal contacts (mostly related to research), and the number of industrial PhDs. We regressed the knowledge sharing performance against a set of independent variables which include three factors reflecting the importance of eight different types of IOs. In addition, we asked respondents to assess seven characteristics of IOs, differentiating between important and unimportant IOs.

The IO factor analysis drew on questions on the perceived importance of 8 different types of IOs for knowledge transfer. The KMO-measure of the analysis is high at 0.79 and the data are therefore well suited for a principal component analysis. A non-orthogonal rotation method was used (Promax) and three factors were extracted. They explain 63% of the variation in the perceived importance of the included IOs. In addition, of the 24 factor loadings (8 organizations times 3 extracted factors), only 2 represented cross-loadings above 0.3 (0.34 and 0.31) – all other cross-loadings are negligible. Hence, the three factors are a suitable representation of the importance of IO types for knowledge sharing in the dataset. Figure 1 below shows the factor loadings.

- Factor 1 comprises organizations supporting spin-offs and IP-based transfers (IO1).
- Factor 2 groups together the organizations that provide support for university-industry collaborations, whether this is in financial or other (networking) form (IO2).
- Factor 3 describes the more elusive effect of internet-based information and networking platforms (IO3).

Data analysis methods

Classical regression models could not be used as the assumption of a normal distribution of the dependent variables was violated due to strong skewness, zero-inflation and overdispersion. To remedy this problem, models of the family of "tweedie distributions" were estimated. Tweedie models allow the adjustment of the distribution shape, as the variance is not linear (as in Poisson models), but an exponential function of the expected value (mean): $VAR(\mu)=\mu^p$, where the parameter p is estimated. The following distribution forms are supported by the model:

- $p=0$: Classical normal distribution
- $p=1$: Poisson distribution
- $1 < p < 2$: Mix of Poisson and Gamma distribution.

Figure 1. Results of the Promax Factor Analysis

Source: FHNW Science Survey (2018).

The Poisson distribution covers zero values, but only allows discrete realisations of the dependent variable and the variance is also equal to the expected value ($\text{VAR}(\mu)=\mu^1$). On the other hand, the gamma distribution does not cover zero values, but allows for contiguous realisations and, at the same time, disproportionate variance. Optimally, the estimated parameter p of the models would thus lie in this range.

The estimation results are presented in the next section. The last three rows report the number of observations n , a pseudo- R^2 as a coefficient of determination between predicted and observed dependent variables, and the estimated link power p between the previously described limits of $1 < p < 2$ for all models. All estimations results were corrected for heteroscedasticity and influential outliers and carried out with the R package "tweedie".

Findings

Intermediary organizations and knowledge transfer performance

We find that commercialization-based and research-based transfer measures are higher, the higher IO1 (IOs supporting spin-offs and IP-based transfers) and IO2 (IOs supporting university-industry cooperation, e.g., financially, via networking) have been rated (Tables 1 and 2). For spin-offs, only IO1-type intermediary organizations matter, i.e., knowledge transfer offices, incubators, innovation/science parks, proof-of-concept and commercialisation funds (Table 2). The estimations show that IOs are generally not involved in industrial doctorates, i.e., doctorates written in cooperation with non-academic partners (Table 1), nor in teaching-based knowledge sharing (Table 3). We even find *fewer* professional education graduates in institutes which gave IO1 a high importance rating. Most likely this does not reflect a direct causality, in the sense that working with IO1 reduces professional education performance, but hints at different profiles and activity patterns with regard to knowledge sharing. Institutes that relied on professional education in their knowledge sharing did not (have to) work with IO1-type intermediary organizations, as their involvement in knowledge commercialisation via start-ups was low.

Internet-based IOs (IO3) are considered as more important by institutes that are very active in transferring their knowledge to users outside science through further education offers (Table 3), but they are significantly less important for institutes focussing on patenting and spin-offs.

Table 1. Intermediary organizations and research-based knowledge sharing.^a

	No. of doctorates with non-academic partners per 10 scientists	Research-based transfers index	Informal transfers index
IO1	+0.033	+0.037*	+0.038**
IO2	-0.152	+0.044**	+0.020+
IO3	+0.076	+0.011	+0.012
Observations	553	477	477
pseudo-R2	0.290	0.390	0.281
Link-power p	1.37	1.12	1.11

** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05, + p < 0.1

^a Controls for type of organization, academic discipline, size of institute, teaching loads, leaders private sector experiences, orientation towards knowledge sharing (mission, incentives, rules) not shown; full estimation results in Barjak, Heimsch, & Maidl (2020).

Table 2. Intermediary organizations and IP-based knowledge sharing.^a

	No. of patent applications per 10 scientists	No. of licence agreements per 10 scientists	No. of new spin-off companies per 10 scientists	No. of older spin-off companies per 10 scientists
IO1	+0.197*	+0.159	+0.220*	+0.306**
IO2	+0.295**	+0.185	-0.149	+0.051
IO3	-0.204**	-0.129	+0.042	-0.393**
Observations	553	560	564	550
pseudo-R2	0.317	0.147	0.306	0.261
Link-power p	1.33	1.39	1.31	1.36

** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05, + p < 0.1

^a See footnote of Table 1.

Table 3. Intermediary organizations and teaching-based knowledge sharing.^a

	No. of BSc/MSc theses with non-academic partners per 10 scientists	No. of professional education graduates per 10 scientists	Index for teaching-based transfers
IO1	+0.090	-0.335*	+0.053**
IO2	-0.021	+0.062	+0.024
IO3	-0.065	+0.175+	+0.020
Observations	553	552	478
pseudo-R2	0.717	0.401	0.294
Link-power p	1.38	1.34	1.46

** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05, + p < 0.1

^a See footnote of Table 1.

Relevant characteristics and activities of intermediary organizations

Respondents were asked to rate the IOs they classified as important or unimportant on five characteristics: 1. organizational proximity (internal vs. external), 2. involvement of private companies, 3. geographical proximity, 4. disciplinary proximity, 5. knowledge of markets.

Furthermore, two activity-related variables, flexibility in the range of services offered and organization of ‘interesting events’, were evaluated.

We calculate and compare the 95%-confidence intervals for these ratings for important and unimportant IOs (Figure 2). We find that important IOs are less strongly perceived as external than unimportant IOs, i.e., they are more considered as internal and parts of the organization. The biggest difference in the ratings appears for field knowledge and specificity: important IOs are considerably more field-specific, whereas unimportant IOs have been evaluated as more interdisciplinary. Important IOs (are perceived to) know markets and customers better than unimportant IOs. Last but not least, IOs perceived as important organize ‘interesting events’ (according to the respondents’ perception) more often than IOs not perceived as important.

Figure 2. IO characteristics and activities for un-/important IOs (95% conf. intervals)

Source: FHNW Science Survey (2018).

Conclusions and practical implications

There is a fairly clear correspondence between the importance and commonness of IP-based and research-related knowledge transfer mechanisms in academic institutes and the importance they attribute to two types of IOs: to IO1 which support spin-offs and IP-based knowledge transfers (such as KTOs, incubators, innovation/science parks, proof-of-concept and commercialisation funds), and to IO2 supporting university-industry cooperation (such as public innovation funders, cooperative research institutes and centres, or thematic networks and cluster organizations). Above all, IO1 and IO2 can support patenting activities, research-based transfers and informal transfers; only IO1 matters for spin-off activities. Type 1 intermediary organizations thus have a slightly broader importance and clearer relationship to knowledge sharing performance than type 2 IOs. Even if a university thus wants to place a focus on research cooperation and contracts with industry, an IO1-type organization might provide more use to scientists than an IO2-type organization, as the former provides valuable complementary knowledge for handling the output of research, e.g., with regard to finding good solutions regarding IP ownership and commercialisation.

For industrial doctorates and teaching-based transfer mechanisms none of the IOs provided any noteworthy influence on institutes’ performance. Other factors, matter more, for instance

the personal contacts to the private sector via double affiliations or previous positions in industry (not shown in the estimates, see Barjak, Heimsch & Maidl, 2020).

Internet-based initiatives (IO3) did not appear as important IOs. However, it must be noted that the survey was conducted before the Covid-19 pandemic and that this might have changed since then. Some observers expect a growing importance of virtual IOs (Albats et al., 2022).

Not only the type of IO matters, but also its structures and activities. It is preferable to reduce organizational distance by setting up an internal IO (at least from the academics' perspective, the industry view might differ on this point). Likewise, cognitive distance is also preferably low (Villani et al., 2017), and IOs in the same discipline and with field knowledge are generally preferred to interdisciplinary IOs. Still, their knowledge should be complementary to the knowledge of academics with regard to aspects of markets and customers. Whereas it does not seem to be crucial whether the service offer of the IOs is flexible and customized to the needs of the scientists on a case-by-case basis, events matter: for important IOs the organization of interesting events was on average higher rated than for unimportant IOs.

The findings provide a better understanding of what mechanisms of knowledge sharing are mainly affected by the work of IOs and which of their activities make a difference for their partners in research and higher education. The findings should help IOs to adjust their approaches and services to better meet the needs of a broader range of research institutes which are their main knowledge sources and therefore an important stakeholder in any attempt to increase knowledge sharing. The findings speak to the owners of the IOs as well which often come from the academic sector and need IOs to support them with their third mission activities. Last but not least, innovation policy makers in many countries (definitely in Switzerland) have strong interest in functioning knowledge sharing, as this is one of the main transmission mechanisms for generating an economic and social impact of higher education organizations.

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